

#16

Evaluation & Impact Assessment APPRAISAL OF GROUP DYNAMICS

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Periodically throughout the interactive innovation process.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small group, 12-15 actors.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical expertise required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Approximately 2 hours.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>No resources required, apart from basic materials.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tool #4.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Teagasc.

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Assess relationships in multi-actor group, focusing on:
 - » Trust
 - » Willingness, ease and openness in sharing information
 - » Effectiveness of the facilitator
 - » General enjoyment of membership of the group
- Decide actions to improve group functioning.

Background and Logic

What characterises a multi-actor approach to interactive innovation is that people with different knowledges, perspectives etc. come together. The process by which different actors interact and feel comfortable sharing their knowledge & perspectives is not without challenges. Some actors (for instance, scientists) can have wide-ranging experience with projects. Other actors may be participating in a project for the very first time. The language and modus operandi of formally organised/ funded projects can be unfamiliar terrain for some. Participation in the form of open sharing of knowledge and perspectives may be hampered by some actors feeling unsure of what they bring to the interactive innovation process: where does their knowledge/ perspective fit in and is it of value, some actors may ask themselves. Facilitators of multi-actor approaches must employ deliberate strategies to support diverse actors to openly contribute to the interactive innovation process. Difference is the 'gold' of the multi-actor approach, and it must be strategically 'mined'.

This tool provides an approach to assess relational dynamics within a multi-actor group, creating a safe environment for group members to assess relational dynamics from their own perspectives. A guide is offered for the group and its facilitators to make improvements to relational dynamics.

Materials

- 'Five Ingredients for Success' infographic.
- A4 size assessment sheet (pdf) – one for each member.
- A0 size assessment sheet
- Sticky discs/stickers – each member to be allocated one per question (10 stickers for each member).

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Group Work: Five Ingredients for Success

Ingredient 1: Membership & Organisation

“We might all be different as individuals but our group has common goals. We as members genuinely believe in and commit to these goals. Our group is well organised and we have a clear idea about how we operate. We have our schedule of meetings well in advance so that we can plan and prepare.”

Ingredient 3: Trust & Security

“In order for use as group to create solutions, we must feel that we can speak openly and truthfully without feeling that what we say might be irrelevant or not useful... We are all different, we speak different languages, and it's important that we show that we value each other's point of view. There's no sense that certain types of knowledge are superior in the group and people are not afraid to speak up.”

Ingredient 2: Social & Emotional Dynamics

“Enjoyment and fun is an important part of how our group works. It makes taking part a more positive experience. We have developed good working relationships and even some friendships. This provides an environment conducive to sharing challenges and to identifying solutions.”

Ingredient 4: Solidarity

“While the proverbial saying ‘a rising tide lifts all boats’ may not be true in many cases, it is a core principle of this group. What we do is relevant to all members and therefore is of interest (and potential benefit) to all members.”

Ingredient 5: Facilitation & Learning Drivers

“We have access to and are exposed to different types of expertise in the group and this is a major driver of the group – it is why we want to be involved. Our group is also expertly facilitated and if we didn’t have that expert facilitation, our group wouldn’t operate as well as it does.”

Self-Appraisal for Groups: Guide for Facilitators

This assessment sheet is designed to assist you to facilitate a structured conversation about how the group you facilitate is functioning and how it might function better. The sheet is divided into five components, which correspond to five key ingredients for successful groups. These key ingredients were identified through research undertaken in Ireland and are consistent with research findings internationally in relation to how groups function at their best.

How to Use The Sheet

1. Distribute a copy of the appraisal sheet to each of the group member present.
2. Allow an appropriate time (10 minutes suggested) for each member to complete the sheet.
3. Prior to the meeting, you will have placed the A0 (flip chart size) version of the appraisal sheet on a flipchart stand.
4. Distribute 10 self-adhesive discs to each group member. All discs should be of the same size and colour.
5. Once the allocated time has elapsed, invite each member to mark their answers onto the A0 size poster on the flipchart. In this way, each individual group member has an equal opportunity to record their views anonymously.

6. Take a short break to visually review the scatter of sticky discs under each question. It is likely that the collective answer i.e. the arrangement of the adhesive discs under each answer will shed some light on group perceptions.
7. Use the questions listed below to prompt further appraisal and reflection within your group. Pose the questions to the group and allow them time to respond. Make sure to acknowledge the questions where the perceptions are positive (you want more of that in the future) as well as probing how to improve the situation where perceptions are less positive/negative (what can we do to improve?).
8. Record the decisions reached and agreed actions, including the individual(s) responsible. Ideally, group members would take responsibility for many of the actions.

SELF APPRAISAL SHEET

1. Do you have shared goals in this group		
members have different goals	We have some shared goals	Many shared goals
2. Is the schedule of meetings clear and predictable		
Sometimes	Most of the time	Always
3. Do you feel comfortable talking truthfully in the group		
Some people don't feel comfortable sharing	Most members feel comfortable, most of the time	Yes, we all feel comfortable sharing
4. Do you think members feel comfortable challenging others within the group		
Sometimes members feel offended by others	There's a challenging but mostly positive atmosphere	We readily and positively challenge eachother
5. Are the meetings enjoyable to attend?		
Sometimes	Most of the time	Always very enjoyable
6. In this group, are the activities relevant and interesting to all members, do you think?		
Sometimes	Most of the time	Always
7. If you were to pick one word to describe this group, what would it be?		
Hard to pick a word	A positive word:	A not so positive word:
8. Can you please comment on the facilitation of this group		
9. Can you give an example of a very well facilitated meeting or event that you attended (name the event, meeting, farm etc.)		
10. Are there any other issues you would like to mention /address?		

Self Appraisal. Full-size form on the next page.

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